

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 66 (2026) 60-73

EISSN 2543-5426

Studies on the effect of different polluted soil on the growth performance of *Cajanus cajan* L.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of different polluted soils on the emergence and growth performance of *Cajanus cajan* L. The experiment was conducted in a screen house under controlled environmental conditions. Different polluted soils obtained from, mechanic workshop (PSM), garbage soil (PSG), soil near power generator (PSP), laundry site (PSL), vehicular roadside (PSR) and soil devoid of pollution (UPS) serves as control. The percentage emergence of the seeds, height, stem girth, number of leaves, leaf area and relative growth rate (RGR) were studied to determine the growth performance of *C. cajan*. The result of the study revealed that the emergence of seeds, heights, stem girth, number of leaves and leaf area of *C. cajan* were mostly reduced in soils derived from PSM, PSP and PSR which are believed to have higher concentrations of crude oil contamination. The plant height at 8 weeks after planting (WAP) was lowest in PSM soil (28.18±2.15 cm), PSP soil (85.66 ±3.46 cm), PSR soil (92.18±4.28 cm) while control soil (UPS) had the tallest plant (124.78±3.76 cm). Leaf area at 8WAP in PSM soil was 1.32±0.28 cm², PSP soil (2.81±0.29 cm²), PSR soil (2.59±1.37 cm²) and PSL soil had leaf area of 4.05±9.06 cm². *C. cajan* had lowest mean number of leaves in PSM soil with 5.80±1.48. The relative growth rate of *C. cajan* was also reduces in PSM soil (0.05±0.01), PSG soil (0.06±0.03) and PSR soil (0.09±0.02) while the plant on control soil (UPS) has 0.20±0.02. Statistical analysis (ANOVA, P≤0.05) showed that significant differences abound in the percentage emergence of seeds, plant heights, number of leaves, leaf area and the relative growth rate. Soil contaminated with crude oil are prone to reduction in soil aeration and microorganisms which have resultant effect on the growth of this plant. The effluent of spent crude oil on agricultural soils should be prevented to avert the reduction in the growth of agricultural crops.

Keywords: *Cajanus cajan*, crude oil, emergence, growth, pollution

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in population is a global issue which has resultant effect on the ecosystem. This has led to an increase in industrialization and anthropogenic activities such as mining, release of industrial waste, smelting of As or incineration of fossil, particularly coal, utilization of As loaded water for irrigation, herbicides and fertilizers [15], thereby affecting the soil flora and fauna and also water requirement of the environment. The release of chemicals, pollute the environment/soil and have adverse effect on humans, animals, flora and fauna. [27] noted that the intensive industrialization, urbanization and industrial wastes contaminate the soil causing food chain to be affected by metals (bioaccumulation). The indiscriminate and rising uses of synthetic fertilizers for the growth of agricultural crops also contaminate the agricultural soils [32]. [30] and [34] noted that contaminated soils with heavy metals is considered as global environmental issue, posing significant risk to human health and the environment. [7] reported that most of the automobile machine dispose of petro derive waste either direct into open soil or into water and irrigation canals ultimately reach agricultural plants.

Soils polluted with these chemicals have adverse effect in reducing plant growth. [4] noted that contamination of soil with spent oil engine lead to significant reduction of moisture content which subsequently induces a considerable reduction in plant growth. This might be due to the fact that there will be changes in the physical and microbial properties of the polluted soil that affect the growth of plants. [33] also noted that the changes in soil due to contamination of soil with petroleum derivative substances can lead to water and oxygen deficit as well as shortage of available forms of nitrogen and phosphorus., this can affect the germinate of seeds.

The effect of oil contaminated soil as reported by [1] could be because the oil acts as a physical barrier preventing or reducing access to the seed, water and oxygen. Also, [5] equally reported that the presence of crude oil in the environment has caused several adverse impacts on the environment.

Crude oil contamination could lead to variation in microbial, physico-chemical, heavy metal and hydrocarbon content of the soil which in turn may affects the biological components of the ecosystem including microbes, insects, vegetation and wild life. [29] reported that heavy metals indirectly affect soil enzymatic activities by shifting the microbial community which synthesizes enzymes.

The polluted soils are reported that it can be harmful to humans by making contact with the soil or consuming vegetables produced from contaminated soil [28]. In the work of [8], it was revealed that more than 70% of soil pollutants are carcinogenic in nature with chances of developing cancer in humans exposed to polluted soils. [13] reported that heavy metals are potentially toxic and phytotoxicity for plants resulting in chlorosis, weak plant growth, yield depression and may even be accompanied by reduced nutrient uptake, disorders in plant metabolism and reduced ability to fix molecular nitrogen in leguminous plants. [20] reported that some of these detrimental effects of heavy metals include disorder of biological activities of the soil toxic effects in plants and harmful effects on human being as a result of entrance into food chain.

Considering the detrimental effect of crude oil polluted soil on the Physico-chemical properties of the soil and the growth of plants, this study examined the effect of different polluted soils on the growth performance of *C. cajan* (Figures 1 & 2).

Figure 1. Photo of a *Cajanus cajan* plant.

Figure 2. Photo of *Cajanus cajan* plant with fruits.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area and Sample Collection

The experiment was carried out in the Greenhouse of the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Faculty of Science, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. Soil samples were collected from the following contaminated sites: soil within the premises of exhaust pipe of heavy power generating plant (PSP), soil within the premises of mechanical workshop (PSM), soil from the premises where laundry water is discharged (PSL), soil from the premises of busy road side (PSR), soil obtained from the garbage (PSG), the sixth sample which was used as the control (UPS) was collected soil from the premises of the Botanical Garden of the Department of Biology, Kwara State College of Education, Oro, Kwara State, Nigeria was labelled as UPS which served as the control.

The soil samples, in each of the location described above were taken from the top soil within 5 cm to 15 cm and then bulked to make bulk samples. Three kilograms (3 kg) of each soil sample (PSP, PSM, PSL, PSR, PSG and UPS) were weighed into plastic pots and replicates five times.

Seed Source

The seeds of *Cajanus cajan* were purchased from the Old Garage market, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The seeds were authenticated in the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. The viable seeds were sorted out and tested for viability using floatation technique according to [17].

Experimental Design

The soil-fed planting pots from each soil samples were used for the experiments. The pots in each sample were divided into 4 sub-groups of 5 pots each and each sub-group was used for the plants stated above.

Thus the treatments were defined as:

PSP_A, PSM_A, PSL_A, PSR_A, PSG_A and UPS_A for *Cajanus cajan*

In each treatment above, 5 viable seeds of each plant were sown in each pot to a depth of one centimetre (1 cm) and were replicated five times. The pots were arranged in the greenhouse of the Department of plant Science and Biotechnology, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti using Completely Block Design (CRD). The pots were wet daily with tap water at 7:00 hr. The seeds were considered germinated upon plumule emergence and the seedlings were thinned to one (1) seedling per pot to avoid overcrowding at 1 week after emergence.

Data Collection

The plumule emergence percentage was calculated using the method of Marli and Denise (2006) as:

$$P (\%) = \frac{nP}{nT} \times 100$$

where: P (%) = Plumule Emergence Percentage

nP = No of plumule emergence

nT = Total no of seeds sown

Measurement of growth parameters consisting of shoot length (using metre rule), stem girth (using Verner calliper), leaf length and leaf breathe (using ruler) were measured and recorded on weekly bases for a period of 12 weeks. Leaf area was calculated according to the method of [17] as:

$$LA = L \times B \times 0.75$$

At 8 weeks after planting, the plants were carefully harvested and the fresh and dry weights determined. The fresh weights were obtained by uprooting the plants from each pot and the roots were carefully washed with clean water to remove soil particles and weighed on a weighing balance (model PN 163). The dry weights were obtained by oven drying the harvested plants at 70 °C for 48 h to get rid of all moisture and ensure a constant weight and then weighed on a weighing balance (Model PN 163).

Data Analysis

The results obtained were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Duncan's multiple range test at $p \leq 0.05$ was used to separate the means.

3. RESULTS

The effect of polluted soil on the emergence percentage of *C. cajan* is shown in Table 1. The plants grown in PSM soil had the least emergence percentage of 36%. The highest emergence % was observed in UPS soils with 72%. Statistical analysis showed that there were significant differences between the emergence percentages of plants grown in the treated soils compared to the control (UPS).

Table 1. Effect of polluted soil on the percentage emergence of the seeds of *Cajanus cajan*.

Treatments	<i>C. cajan</i>
PSM	36d
PSG	48b
PSP	44c
PSL	44c
PSR	52b
UPS	72a

Means with the same letter within columns are not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$)

PSM = polluted soils obtained from mechanic workshop; PSG= garbage soil; PSP = soil near power generator; PSL = laundry site soil; PSR = vehicular roadside soil and UPS = soil devoid of pollution i.e. agricultural land serves as control.

The effect of polluted soil on the height of *Cajanus cajan* is shown in Table 2. The plant height at one week after planting (1WAP) was highest in PSR treatment (47.80 cm) and lowest in the PSM treatment (20.18 cm). Statistical analysis shows that no significant differences abound among the height of plants in PSG, PSL and PSR with mean values of 46.18cm, 47.36 cm and 47.80 cm respectively. At 1 WAP, significant differences abound in heights of plants grown in PSM, PSG, PSL and PSR when compared to the control. PSP and UPS plant heights showed no significant difference. At 8 weeks after planting (8WAP), the mean plant height was highest in the control experiment UPS (124.78 cm) while the lowest mean plant height was found in the PSM treatment (28.18 cm). The mean plant height of PSL treatment and that of the control experiment (UPS) were also 117.78 cm and 124.78 cm respectively. At 8 WAP, there were significant differences in plant height between the treatments (PSM, PSG, PSP, and PSR) when compared to the control except the PSL treatment that showed no significant difference to the control.

Table 2. Effect of polluted soil on the plant height (cm) of *Cajanus cajan*.

Weeks after Planting (WAP)								
Treatment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PSM	20.18±1.15	21.86±2.79	22.44±2.51	24.10±3.08	24.86±2.19	25.96±2.03	27.46±2.67	28.18±2.15
PSG	46.18±6.99	42.94±7.35	44.32±6.78	53.04±7.09	53.58±4.65	53.60±4.27	70.26±3.44	73.32±6.47
PSP	34.52±13.23	38.04±15.92	42.20±2.43	42.84±2.04	51.90±3.16	72.18±3.37	78.64±7.39	85.66±3.46
PSL	47.36±4.19	49.70±3.11a	49.48±1.95	50.58±3.71	62.28±5.75	62.92±4.28	72.92±2.28	117.78±17.96
PSR	47.80±5.04	47.86±5.19	51.00±5.90	55.28±4.94	58.20±3.56	75.84±4.49	88.80±3.66	92.18±4.28
UPS	31.24±3.89	33.22±5.79	55.02±7.89	58.94±1.14	70.76±6.16	86.06±2.86	103.30±2.58	124.78±3.76

Means followed by the same letter within column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$

PSM = polluted soils obtained from mechanic workshop; PSG = garbage soil; PSP = soil near power generator; PSL = laundry site soil; PSR = vehicular roadside soil and UPS = soil devoid of pollution i.e. agricultural land serves as control.

The effect of polluted soil on the stem girth of *C. cajan* is shown in Table 3. *C. cajan* stem girth at 1 week planting (1WAP), was highest in control UPS (1.06 cm) and lowest in the treatment PSM (0.56 cm). At 8 weeks after planting (8WAP), the control experiment (UPS) has the highest mean girth (2.14 cm) while the treatment (PSM) has the lowest mean girth (1.30 cm). The mean stem girth of the treatments PSP and PSR were closely similar to that of the control likewise those of the PSG (1.64 cm) and PSL (1.80 cm) were closely similar.

Table 3. Effect of polluted soil on the stem girth (cm) of *Cajanus cajan*.

Weeks after Planting (WAP)								
Treatment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PSM	0.56±0.09	0.60±0.07	0.60±0.12	0.62±0.08	0.76±0.21	0.80±0.24	0.88±0.68	1.30±0.16
PSG	0.82±0.08	0.80±0.16	0.92±0.08	1.20±0.16	1.16±1.17	1.12±0.14	1.34±0.09	1.64±0.28
PSP	0.82±0.08	1.00±0.16	1.06±0.11	1.08±0.08	1.09±0.08	1.18±0.08	1.56±0.08	2.04±0.23
PSL	1.04±0.13	1.08±0.08	1.10±0.07	1.12±0.08	1.12±0.13	1.18±0.13	1.52±0.19	1.80±0.16
PSR	0.78±0.45	1.02±0.18b	1.14±0.05	1.14±0.11	1.26±0.05	1.56±0.38	1.62±0.08	2.02±0.19
UPS	1.06±0.09	1.24±0.05	1.28±0.04	1.38±0.08	1.38±0.13	1.54±0.26	2.14±0.11	2.14±0.17

Means followed by the same letter within column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$

PSM = polluted soils obtained from mechanic workshop; PSG = garbage soil; PSP = soil near power generator; PSL = laundry site soil; PSR = vehicular roadside soil and UPS = soil devoid of pollution i.e. agricultural land serves as control.

At 1 week after planting (1WAP), ANOVA revealed that the stem girth of *C. cajan* of PSL soil was not significantly different from the control while other soil i.e. PSM, PSG, PSP and PSR were significantly different from the control (UPS). Statistical Analysis (ANOVA, $P \leq 0.05$) showed that the mean stem girth of *C. cajan* at 8 week (8WAP), in PSP and PSR treatments were not significantly different from the control (UPS). Other treatments PSM, PSG and PSL were significantly different from the control (UPS).

The effect of polluted soil on the number of leaves of *C. cajan* as shown in Table 4 revealed that the mean number of leaves of *C. cajan* at 1 week after planting (1WAP) was highest in plant grown in the control UPS (3.80) and lowest in PSM (2.00) treatment. The mean number of leaves in PSG, PSP, PSL and PSR were 3.40, 3.20, 3.00 and 3.40 respectively. At 8WAP, the mean number of leaves was highest in the PSR (29.20) treatment and lowest in the PSM (5.80) treatment. Other treatments varied in number. PSG (16.80), PSP (21.80) and PSL (18.00) while that of the control (UPS) was 26.20. Statistical Analysis (ANOVA, $P \leq 0.05$) showed that the mean number of leaves of *C. cajan* at 1WAP, PSG and PSR treatments were not significantly different from the control while PSM, PSP and PSL were significantly different from the control. At 8WAP, ANOVA showed that the mean number of leaves of *C. cajan* in the treatments were significantly different from the control except the PSR that was not significant different from the control (UPS).

Table 4. Effects of polluted soil on the number of leaves of *Cajanus cajan*.

Weeks after Planting (WAP)								
Treatment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PSM	1.40±0.55	2.20±0.45	3.40±1.14	3.60±0.55	3.60±0.81	4.20±0.80	4.40±0.45	4.40±0.71
PSG	4.40±0.89	5.40±0.55	8.99±2.83	14.00±2.00	27.00±15.66	26.00±3.53	31.20±5.93	34.40±5.89
PSP	4.00±0.55	5.00±0.71	5.60±1.34	10.40±0.89	13.40±2.19	15.60±2.61	15.80±1.48	16.80±2.28
PSL	5.60±0.54	6.80±1.30	9.40±1.67	18.20±2.49	26.20±2.68	26.40±4.34	27.00±3.87	27.60±4.01
PSR	4.40±0.55	4.60±0.55	4.60±0.89	8.80±1.64	20.60±3.44	21.00±3.16	22.60±1.67	23.60±1.67
UPS	3.80±1.79	4.20±1.79	5.20±1.09	12.60±2.79	24.60±2.41	28.40±2.61	27.20±1.64	29.20±1.09

Means followed by the same letter within column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$

PSM = polluted soils obtained from mechanic workshop; PSG = garbage soil; PSP = soil near power generator; PSL = laundry site soil; PSR = vehicular roadside soil and UPS = soil devoid of pollution i.e. agricultural land serves as control.

The result of the effect of polluted soil on the mean leaf area of *C. cajan* revealed that the mean leaf area of *C. cajan* at 1 week after planting (1WAP) was highest in PSR (1.61 cm²) and the control UPS (1.59 cm²) and lowest in PSM (0.59 cm²). The mean leaf area of other treatments (PSG, PSP and PSL) is 1.09 cm², 1.03 cm² and 1.36 cm² respectively. At 8WAP, the PSL plants had the highest mean leaf area (4.05 cm²) while PSM has the lowest mean value of 1.32 cm² (Table 5). PSG, PSP and PSR soil have 2.39 cm², 2.81 cm² and 2.59 cm² respectively while the control experiment had 3.82 cm². Statistical Analysis (ANOVA, $P \leq 0.05$) showed

that the mean leaf area of *C. cajan* at 1WAP in PSL and PSR treatments were not significantly different from the control (UPS) while other treatments PSM, PSG and PSP were significantly different from the control experiment (UPS). At 8 WAP, mean leaf area of PSL was not significantly different from the control (UPS) while other treatments PSM, PSG, PSP and PSR were significantly different from the control (UPS).

Table 5. Effects of polluted soil on the leaf area (cm²) of *Cajanus cajan*.

Weeks after Planting (WAP)								
Treatment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PSM	0.59±0.11	0.68±0.04	0.69±0.08	0.71±0.06	0.81±0.32	0.92±0.17	1.14±0.16	1.32±0.28
PSG	1.09±0.31	1.23±0.32	1.37±0.45	1.50±0.54	1.62±0.43	1.71±0.58	2.14±0.38	2.39±0.68
PSP	1.03±0.04	1.12±0.13	1.14±0.11	1.15±0.19	1.44±0.33	1.84±0.26	2.60±0.32	2.81±0.29
PSL	1.36±0.41	1.39±0.56	1.50±0.36	1.50±0.50	2.18±1.41	2.53±0.48	2.62±1.64	4.05±6.06
PSR	1.61±0.29	2.01±0.57	2.02±0.31	2.11±0.47	2.29±0.45	2.35±0.20	2.45±0.83	2.59±1.37
UPS	1.59±0.31	1.69±0.23	1.79±0.23	1.93±0.34	2.55±0.27	3.06±0.89	3.45±0.51	3.82±0.68

Means followed by the same letter within column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$
 PSM = polluted soils obtained from mechanic workshop; PSG = garbage soil; PSP = soil near power generator; PSL = laundry site soil; PSR = vehicular roadside soil and UPS = soil devoid of pollution i.e. agricultural land serves as control.

The effect of polluted soils on the relative growth rate of *C. cajan* is shown in Table 6. Plant grown in PSM soil had RGR of 0.05±0.01, PSG soil (0.06±0.03), PSP and PSL soils had 0.13 ±0.07 respectively, PSR soil (0.09±0.02) while those plants in the control UPS had 0.20 ±0.02. Statistical analysis revealed that significant differences were observed in the RGR of plants grown in the polluted soils compared to the control. RGR of plants in PSM and PSG soils were not significantly different from each other.

Table 6. Effect of polluted on the Relative Growth Rate (cm) of *Cajanus cajan*.

Treatment	<i>Cajaus cajan</i>
PSM	0.05±0.01
PSG	0.06±0.03
PSP	0.13±0.07
PSL	0.13±0.03
PSR	0.09±0.02
UPS	0.20±0.02

Means follow by the same letter within column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$
PSM = polluted soils obtained from mechanic workshop; PSG = garbage soil; PSP = soil near power generator; PSL = laundry site soil; PSR = vehicular roadside soil and UPS = soil devoid of pollution i.e. agricultural land serves as control.

4. DISCUSSION

The growth of *C. cajan* in this study was mostly impaired / reduced on soil polluted by engine or crude oil. The emergence percentage of the plant was reduced by the polluted soils mostly that of mechanical workshop. This observation agreed with the work of [1] who reported reduction in germination rate in some plant species caused by petroleum contaminants.

This could be as a result of the soil being contaminated with the oil hydrocarbons that block the soil aeration thereby leads to lack of oxygen, nitrogen and eventually death of microorganisms in the soil. This activities resulted in reducing the physiological growth such as plant heights, stem girth, leaf area, most especially in mechanical workshop soils.

The stem girth of *C. cajan* was reduced in plants grown in soils obtained from mechanical workshop which might be as a result of oil spillage on the soil which might have blocked the translocation processes needed by the plants during water and mineral nutrients absorption.

This result conform with the earlier assertion of [12] who noted that petroleum hydrocarbons can reach the soil from many sources including oil spillages by transportation vessels, pipelines, leakages, automobile servicing stations, fuel stations and other anthropogenic activities.

The reduction in all the growth parameters of the mechanical workshops might be as a result of the presence of oil in the soil that block the soil oxygen, water, nutrient uptake by the roots of plants and reduction in translocation of minerals from the roots up to the shoot of the plants. The result corroborates the work of [20] and [21] who emphasised that the presence of spent engine oil in the soil plant micro-environment affects normal soil chemical, nutrient release and uptake as well as reduction in availability of water.

The polluted soil was observed to affect the *C. cajan* grown in soil near power generator having oil contaminant as the plumule emergence plant height, stem girth and number of leaves were greatly reduced. This observation agreed with the work of [18] who reported that contaminated soil with diesel adversely affected the height, number of leaves, stem diameter, hypocotylar and epicotylar lengths, cotyledonary area per seedling, total leaf area, dry biomass of shoot and root of *Thespesia populrea*. [3] and [24] noted the reduction in the plant height in petroleum contaminated polluted soil could be due to reduction in nutrients contents of soil since petroleum products are known to reduce nitrogen availability in the soil. Also, this report is in accordance with the work of [2] who observed that the treatment of soils with crude automobile gasoline and spent engine oil significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) delayed the time of germination, percentage germination, height, leaf production and biomass of *V. unguiculata*. [25] and [23] noted that the contamination by diesel can kill the roots and thus preventing the plants from taking up water and under nutrients.

Likewise, [16] reported that crude oil contamination affects the heights of plants. Also, [26] noted that decrease in heights and girths of plants in crude oil- polluted soil may be due to the non-availability of adequate water which possibly affects the nutrient uptake and mobility.

The study showed that the composition of crude oil in soil through oil spillage on agricultural land or effluent from power generator or roadsides near vehicular movement might have a considerable adverse effect on the germination, plant physiology, ecology and agronomic growth and developments of *C. cajan*. The study shows that *C. cajan* cannot grow well on oil polluted soils. Oil contaminated soils needs to be remediated. This can be done through phytoremediation methods to clean up the contaminants. [14] refers to phytoremediation as the use of plants to clean up contaminants soils. Also [9] reported that phytoremediation using plants to remove metal pollutants from soil can provide cost effective, long lasting, aesthetic and technical advantages over traditional engineering techniques.

Apart from the oil spillage in soils, toxicity of metals in the garbage soil can also have adverse effect on plants as findings of this study revealed negative effect of garbage soil on plant height, stem girth and leaf area of *C. cajan*. Toxicity of metals in this soil might have been responsible for this effect. [31] reported that effect of Aluminium on *C. cajan* is initially in root growth inhibition, resulting in lesser exploration of bulk soil leading to reduced uptake of water and nutrients. Also, [10] reported that growth reduction in plants growing on heavy metal polluted soils was as a result of the toxicity present in the soil. Likewise, [11] noted that plant growing on heavy metal polluted soils shows a reduction in growth due to the changes in their physiological and biochemical activities. Furthermore, Al toxicity was reported to have a steep decline in the content of chlorophylls [19].

5. CONCLUSION

The results in this study revealed that the effect of soils with spent crude engine oils, effluent generator and roadside contaminated soil was more pronounced on *C. cajan* growth performance. The germination, height, stem girth as well as leaf areas of the plant were more affected than the one grown in garbage or laundry soils. The drastic reduction in the growth parameters in the polluted soils might be as a result of their effects in water uptake, aeration, nutrient bioavailability as well as effect on microorganisms in the soil. There is need for proper awareness on the indiscriminate disposal and uses of spent crude engine oil, power generator, laundry and garbage which might in turn affect the physiological and biochemical activities of plants.

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